

The use of games in a graduation course in an engineering faculty

José Geraldo de Oliveira Rangel Salibi, Bruna Andrade Machado, José de Souza Rodrigues, Fernando Bernardi Souza, Renato de Campos

Department of Engineering Production, Engineering Faculty of Bauru, State University of São Paulo – UNESP, Bauru, Brazil

Email: jose.rangel@unesp.br, bruna.a.machado@unesp.br, jose.rodrigues@unesp.br, fernando.bernardi@unesp.br

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5096805>

Abstract

The quality of education did not accompany the Brazilian effort to increase the number of students in higher education, contributing to this the small number of practical classes and interdisciplinarity.

The publication in 2019 of the new National Curriculum Guidelines changed the focus of content-based teaching to teaching focused on skills development. Game-Based Learning (GBL) generates greater engagement, motivates action, promotes learning and problem solving in a creative way and reduces resistance in the face of complex themes.

In the researched institution it was observed that since 1999 there are experiences with the development and use of games. Among the games found there are simulations and games in digital and board format. The main games used are the Beer Distribution Game and the Lean Board Game, in board format, and the games Bomburguer, Lemonade Stand Game, Virtual Market, Strategy and Sustainability Simulation, Strategy Simulation, Production Planning Simulation, Simulated Model in PROMODEL, Kanban Game and Distribution Game. The games found focus on teaching production management and logistics, strategy and sustainability. Some of the games used focus more on the technical aspects of a specific concept, such as the Lean Board Game, Kanban Game and Goldratt Simulator games.

Production Engineering courses has many interfaces with other areas and there are possibilities to expand the use of games in that institution, contributing to the improvement of teaching and expanding the use of active methodologies in its courses. The research is a case study and was carried out in the following stages: the first sought to find the games used in a course, then the games used in the area and, finally, compared the curriculum with the games found in the area. It is concluded that there is space to expand the use of games and, consequently, the adoption of active methodologies in the analyzed course.

Keywords: Serious Games; Game-based learning; Production Engineering Course.

1 Introduction

The professional trained in Production Engineering must have skills that enable him not only to make physical-technological changes, but also to conduct economic and social changes in the reality that surrounds him (Nakao, 2018). In this way, it acts to design, improve, and implement sustainable production systems for goods and services. For this, it must combine resources of different natures, such as information, equipment, materials, people and energy (Batalha, 2008). It is concluded, therefore, that the interdisciplinary nature is intrinsic to the activity of the Production Engineer.

However, there are obstacles for the training of engineers able to face the challenges faced by the society of the 21st century. Among the biggest bottlenecks present in the current formation of the Production Engineer, stand out, among others, the low volume of practical classes and the challenges of interdisciplinarity (Velho, Costa & Goulart, 2019). Corroborating this, Pavanello, Germano & Freitas-Lemes (2017) affirm: "despite the interdisciplinarity in engineering courses being characterized as a crucial step for the formation of more qualified and prepared professionals for the current job market, actions with this focus they are still few and isolated".

Parallel to this, engineering education presents itself as a promising field for the application of the so-called active teaching methodologies. According to Barbosa & Moura (2014), what differentiates an active learning environment from another that is passive is the "active attitude of intelligence", as opposed to the "passive

attitude of intelligence". Therefore, in an active perspective, the student must make use of his mental functions, such as observing, reflecting, thinking, combining, understanding, reasoning, among others.

Going further, several authors point to the effectiveness of active learning compared to traditional methods. Through active methodologies, students feel more able to apply the knowledge developed in practical situations, learn to express themselves better and improve their interpersonal skills when interacting with classmates. With the use of active methodologies, students can better understand the convergence between different disciplines (dos Santos, 2017), a fact that encourages an interdisciplinary view during the learning process. In addition, placing themselves in an autonomous posture, they acquire a taste for problem solving, while experiencing situations that demand decision-making on their own (Ribeiro, 2005; Silberman, 1996). This is also stated by Fontes & Gontijo (2020), who, in addition, adds encouragement to the critical formation of the individual as an important advantage of using active methodologies.

So, if engineering is a promising field for the implementation of methodologies capable of meeting demands in relation to practical classes and interdisciplinarity, why does your teaching have deficits precisely in these aspects?

In view of the exposed incongruence, an important reflection arises: "how can universities adapt their teaching methods so that the current challenges in engineering education are overcome?"

An alternative to this problem may be to encourage the "active attitude of intelligence" through active teaching methodologies. Among them, the application of games with didactic purposes stands out, because according to Gunther, Kiesling & Stummer (2011), they have a recognized potential to supply several learning deficiencies, such as the student's lack of motivation. Nevertheless, according to Da Matta (2020), keeping in mind the different options of providing practical experiences, the use of simulators is emphasized, among them, games with educational purposes, which constitute a possible alternative to make pedagogical practices more active, dynamic and fun. Combining game-based learning with the use of adequate resources, good theoretical references and an interdisciplinary approach, the use of games is capable of providing effective learning that meets the requirements of modern education (Greipl, Moeller & Ninaus, 2020).

Furthermore, it is pertinent to highlight the profile of the engineering faculty in which this research was carried out. With regard to geographic location, the research institution is a public university located in the state of São Paulo, Brazil. According to the information available on the college's website, it was founded in 1967 and appears on the list of the 400 best universities in the world, in a ranking of eight thousand institutions. Locally, it is present in the ranking of the Top 10 best universities in Latin America, according to Times Higher Education (THE) and the Superior Council for Scientific Investigations (CSIC), as can be seen in its 2020 and 2021 rankings, respectively. Therefore, the chosen university, despite being classified as a relatively young university, is in a position of great relevance with regard to the training of Brazilian engineers. Due to these characteristics, the choice of the faculty in which this research was carried out is justified.

That said, this work set out to investigate "The use of games in a graduation course in an engineering faculty", with the main objective of identifying the types of games used, through the application of a questionnaire with the professors of Production Engineering courses at said institution. Reaching these objectives, the present work can support a possible proposal to improve the curriculum, to be sent to the council of the mentioned course. However, it is important to highlight that the results of this research refer to the context of the investigated faculty, and that the use of games in teaching, despite being a promising practice, must be calibrated to the specifics of each reality. Therefore, the authors hope that this article can serve as an inspiration for new research and methodologies to be considered in the teaching of engineering, not only at this university, but also in other institutions in Brazil and around the world.

2 Literature Review

In contrast to traditional classes (lecture), characterized by expository teaching, we have active methodologies. To explain the basic precepts that guide active teaching methodologies, it is possible to recall the Chinese proverb uttered by the thinker Confucius, even before Christ: "What I hear, I forget; what I see, I remember;

what I do, I understand". Going further, it is prudent not to forget the importance of not only doing but feeling what is being done. This is because the feeling associated with an experience can be a preponderant factor for the fixation of knowledge. In this way, active methodologies, by stimulating high-level mental tasks, such as analysis, synthesis and evaluation, fit perfectly with the demands present in the current teaching of engineering (Silberman, 1996; Fontes & Gontijo, 2020).

2.1 Problem-based Learning

Problem-based learning consists of using contextualized problem situations, real or not, to guide the learning process. In this method, the student ceases to be a passive receiver and becomes the center of the process, while the professor acts as an advisor for the working groups. Although its application varies according to the level and type of education, as well as with the area of knowledge and with the learning objectives, in general terms, the problem-based learning involves the following steps: Beginning; Generation of Ideas; Analyze; Elaboration of Questions; Learning Objective; Synthesis and Evaluation; Study and Presentation (Barbosa & Moura, 2014).

2.2 Project-based Learning

In summary, the purpose of project-based learning is to use projects as a pedagogical resource. Projects are carried out based on the problems, needs, opportunities or interests of individuals. Thus, students must make efforts with a determined time and scope in order to achieve a final goal. The characteristics of project-based learning are of great relevance for engineering training. As a teaching method, the project for educational purposes must have four essential phases: Intention; Planning; Execution; Judgment (Barbosa & Moura, 2014; Venturini & Silva, 2018).

2.3 Team-based Learning

This method seeks to improve not only the results of the learning process, but also to develop collaborative work skills. For this, a structure that involves management of learning teams, preparation and application tasks, constant feedback and evaluation among colleagues is used. The implementation of team-based learning is structured in modules that involve prior preparation and application, both in class and out of class, by the student. After the main concepts are discussed, the teams must solve application tasks, usually of the "problem solving" type, which become increasingly complex and stimulating (Oliveira, Araújo & Veit, 2016).

2.4 Flipped Classroom

This strategy, also known as "inverted classroom", has been gaining more and more prominence, this because it aims to optimize the time in the classrooms. For this, the professor can create a video lecture, screencast or vodcasts that teach students the concept of the subject. Thus, the content can be consumed by students in advance, allowing more free time in the classroom for more engaging and collaborative activities between students and professors (Milman, 2012).

2.5 Gamification

The Gamification is based on the principle that, in general, people do not feel as capable in real life as in games. In real life, when faced with obstacles, people tend to feel depressed, overwhelmed and frustrated, feelings that are not present in the gaming environments. Thus, gamification consists of implementing, in everyday situations and in productive activities, elements present in games, so that people feel more stimulated, influenced and motivated. To achieve this purpose, this method uses a series of design, process and system principles to direct the behavior of individuals, groups and communities (Huang & Soman, 2013).

2.6 Game-based learning

In view of the countless methodologies considered active, the use of games presents itself as a viable alternative in relation to the reality of most educational institutions. Thus, it is important to highlight that games with a didactic purpose can be applied from the perspective of different approaches, for the development of different skills. Among them, we can highlight those related to production operations (Denami, 2018). Similarly,

they are used for strategic simulations within countless contexts, especially for the improvement of skills related to: business, management and professionalism (Zyda, 2005).

According to Cheek et al. (2015), games enable the creation of safe and responsive environments, allowing users to model, test and change new scenarios, according to their application needs. Another important characteristic is that this learning tool provides the systemic experience of the largest number of human and organizational skills possible, since students must seek to mobilize all the knowledge previously acquired in order to obtain a good performance during the game. In addition, games with a cooperative purpose function as an instrument of articulation and promote the educational process, being able to bring motivation and a feeling of inclusion to students, stimulating creativity, spontaneity and valuing the effort of others, which allows for growth synergy of all participants (Amaral, 2009; Greipl, Moeller & Ninaus, 2020).

Nevertheless, according to Connolly et al. (2012), the use of games is promising in relation to the stimulation of a wide range of cognitive skills, such as: concentration, attention and memory. Regarding behavioral skills, Fleming et al. (2017) highlights the development of characteristics essential to managers, to be highlighted: empathy, engagement and effectiveness. Finally, when it comes to games with a focus on decision making, skills such as holistic vision and systemic thinking are developed, as students must consider several variables when making their decisions (Whalen et al, 2018). It should also be noted that all the skills scored are recognized as crucial to excellence in resource management., which is very important to Production Engineers.

2.7 Other active methodologies

In addition to the methodologies presented, there are countless others that could be highlighted, this because teaching is a dynamic area in which, increasingly, new ways of meeting the needs of the teaching and learning process have been sought. Among these methodologies, we highlight: Challenge Based Learning, Peer Instruction, Just-in-Time Teaching, Simulations, Inquiry-based Learning, Think-Pair-Share, among others. Therefore, it is important to make it clear that one of the limitations of this work is characterized precisely by the impossibility of raising all available active methodologies. In addition, it is worth mentioning that many of these methodologies are analogous and / or complement each other, and the final aim is always the same: to stimulate the active attitude of intelligence. For this research, we sought to highlight different methodologies that are not redundant with each other, that is, which are not based entirely on the same principles and concepts of application.

3 Method

To conduct this research, which aims to “identify the types of games used, based on an opinion survey with the professors of that institution regarding the use of games”, the form tool provided by Google, known as “Google Forms”. The created form consisted of 3 sections and 6 questions, 5 of which are mandatory. After its creation, it was sent to the professors of the Production Engineering departments, of three campuses, of the referred institution.

The first section was dedicated to the use of educational methodologies and games in the teaching of Production Engineering (PE). The purpose of this section was to identify the degree of knowledge and use, on the part of teachers, regarding active teaching methodologies. For this, the following question was elaborated: “For the teaching methodologies below, check the most appropriate alternative for your case”, In the question, 7 teaching methodologies were listed, along with options that should be checked by the teachers.

The second section, called “Game-Based Learning”, had the purpose: to identify the teachers' opinion regarding the application of games in the classroom. Thus, the following question was elaborated: “Regarding the use of games in the classroom, you:” with 5 answer options, so that the respondents would say if they agree with the use of games and if they use them to teach classes.

With regard to the last section, “games for teaching PE”, the objective was to survey the games already used by teachers at the institution. Thus, the following question was presented: “Of the games below, choose the most appropriate alternative for your case”, followed by 14 game options (of the most varied types) directly or indirectly related to production engineering, so that, the teachers pointed out if they knew them and if they

used them. In addition, the question was also asked: "What other game (s) do you use in your classes?", With a field for the answer to be typed. Finally, it was asked: "In your opinion, what is the most appropriate game format to support the teaching process?", So that they could choose between "physical / non-digital", "virtual / digital" or "both are equally important ". The results of this section are shown throughout item 4.3.

Regarding the structure of the form, the teachers who, in the second section, answered that they use games, were directed to answer the questions in the third, and last, section, while those who answered that did not use games were directed to the conclusion and sending the questionnaire. The links to the involved games are listed in table 1.

Table 1. Links of the games involved in the survey.

Game	Link
Automania	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/176544/automania
Automobile	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/39351/automobile
Beer Game	https://beergame.masystem.se/
Bomburguer	http://bomburguer.net/Home.aspx
Distribution Game	https://web.lemoyne.edu/~wright/trucks.htm
Goldratt Simulator	https://www.yumpu.com/pt/document/view/62445859/goldratt-simulator
Healthy Heart Hospital	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/186721/healthy-heart-hospital
Imagine	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/191894/imagine
In the Loop	https://intheloopgame.com/
Kanban Game	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/109276/kanban-drivers-edition
Lean Board Game	http://leanboardgame.com/
Lemonade Stand Game	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/173560/lemonade-stand-game
Mobility Game	http://civitas.eu/cs/tool-inventory/mobility-serious-game
Oh My Goods!	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/183840/oh-my-goods
Platform Kahoot	https://kahoot.com/
Production Dice Game	https://www.vlerick.com/en/research-and-faculty/knowledge-items/knowledge/the-production-dice-game
Sustainability	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/30490/sustainability
The Manhattan Project	https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/177249/manhattan-project-chain-reaction
Virtual Market	http://mercadovirtualfeb.com.br/

Note: only games with digital format and / or with a promotion website are listed. The games not included in this list are found only in physical format and / or do not have a publicity website.

4 Results

The questionnaire was sent to 35 teachers from 3 different campuses. Of the total, 22 responded and 13 did not. Among the respondents, 9 use games and, therefore, were sent to answer all questions on the form (sections 1 to 3), while 13 do not use them, limiting themselves to answering only the questions in sections 1 and 2.

4.1 Results of the first section of the form

The first section aimed to identify the degree of knowledge about active teaching methodologies, in relation to the traditional method ("lecture") of expository classes. For this, the following question was posed: "For the

teaching methodologies below, check the most appropriate alternative for your case". The result is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Visual representation of the responses in the first section.

Analysis: it is noted that most teachers make use of traditional classes ("lecture") and that the level of application of teachers in relation to other methodologies is still low, with higher levels for the use of "Problem Based Learning" and "Project Based Learning".

4.2 Results of the second section of the form

The second section aimed to identify the teachers' opinion regarding the application of games in the classroom. Thus, the following question was elaborated: "With regard to the use of games in the classroom, you: ". The result is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Visual representation referring to the answers in section 2

Analysis: in total, 16 (72.7%) teachers agree with the use of games, 6 (27.3%) have no formed opinion and none (0%) disagrees with its application. An interesting fact is that, some of the teachers who claim to use games for teaching, are unaware of the concepts of "Game Based Learning".

4.3 Results of the third section of the form

Finally, the objective of the last section was to survey the games already used by the institution's teachers. Thus, three questions were asked.

First question: "From the following games, choose the most suitable alternative for you".

In this case, of the 14 games presented, 2 were not known by the teachers: the "Healthy Heart Hospital" and the "Oh My Goods", while the best known were the "Lean Board Game" (4 citations) and the " Beer Game "(3 quotes). Regarding the games they use in their classes, there were 4 games mentioned: "Sustainability", "Virtual Market", "Kanban" and "Bomburguer". While some mention having already used: "The Manhattan Project: Chain Reaction", "Lean Board Game", "Kanban" and "Beer Game".

Second question: "What other game (s) do you use in your classes?".

In this field, teachers were free to present other games they use in the classroom. As a result, different titles were cited, such as: "Distribution Game", "Lemonade Stand Game", "Goldratt Simulator", "Production Dice Game", "SDE Strategy Game (LDP)", "Pin Board", "Platform Kahoot", "Lean Factory", "Hunt the Vampire" and

"Imagine". Among these games, the most cited were "Dice Games" and "Goldratt Simulator" (2 quotes). All the others were mentioned only once.

Third question: "In your opinion, what is the most suitable game format to support the teaching process?"

As a last question, we sought to identify the teachers' preferences, considering that the game formats have peculiarities (degree of socialization, immediate feedback, agility to understand the rules). It was noted that the majority of teachers who use games believe that both formats are important, followed by the preference for virtual / digital games.

Figure 3. Visual representation regarding the answers to the third question in section 3.

Analysis: it was noted that the majority of professors who use games believe that both formats are important, followed by the preference for virtual / digital games.

5 Conclusion

According to the consensus perceived in the bibliographic works, it is known that the use of games as a teaching method is a promising practice, precisely because of its ability to work on two of the biggest bottlenecks present in the current training of engineers: the lack of practical classes and the challenges of interdisciplinarity. With regard to the university where the research was carried out, a curriculum structure more aligned with active teaching methodologies was to be expected, due to its youthfulness.

In relation to the objectives that justify this research, it was possible to identify that the majority opinion of professors who teach at that institution, in relation to the use of games, is favorable. Illustratively, 72.6% of the professors agree with the use of games in teaching, while only 27.3% have no formed opinion on the subject, as shown in graph 2. However, this favorable opinion does not translate into the application practice of this method, since only 9, among the 22 respondents, use or have used games to teach their students.

In addition, 13 games currently used by the university's Production Engineering professors were identified. In general, it was found that professors who apply games tend to use more than one game in their classes. However, many of the games traditionally used in teaching Production Engineering are not known to most professors, such as the "Beer Game". This reveals that, in fact, this theme is not yet widely spread among the institution's professors, and this is not an exclusive feature of this university, as can be seen through the work of Barbosa & Moura (2014).

Another important point is the slight preference for virtual games, which may be the result of the current pandemic (by Coronavirus) scenario that still plagues the country, making it impossible to apply games in person.

Among the biggest difficulties faced to carry out this research, it points out the impossibility of raising all the available active methodologies, this because, in the case of an extremely dynamic field, there are numerous methods being created every day (although most of them are redundant). In addition, the reported results refer to the specific context in which the faculty studied is inserted. Thus, as recommendations for future research, the authors recommend that its scope be expanded, that is, that new methodologies be included. It

is also warned that the results of the use of games may vary according to the peculiarities of each situation and, therefore, their application must be calibrated to the specifics of each reality.

Ultimately, it was realized the existence of a promising future for games, allowing them to gain more and more space in classrooms. Specifically, in relation to the target university of this research, the positive position of the professors regarding the use of active methodologies, especially the use of game-based learning, was clear. Despite this, there is still considerable scope for other teaching methods, in addition to the traditional one, to be put into practice.

In a macro scenario, as a future perspective, it is expected that not only the use of games, but any other method available and capable of involving students can gain their space, so that educational challenges can be overcome and a generation of engineers more aligned to the demands of 21st century society can be formed.

Acknowledgements

This study was financed in part by the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior – Brasil (CAPES) – Finance Code 001.

6 References

- Amaral, J. (2009). *Jogos Cooperativos* (4th ed.). São Paulo: Phorte
- Barbosa, E., & Moura, D. (2014). *Metodologias ativas de aprendizagem no ensino de engenharia*. Brazil.
- Batalha, M. (2008). *Introdução à Engenharia de Produção*. Brazil: Elsevier.
- Cheek, C., et al. (2015). *Integrating health behavior theory and design elements in serious games* (Vol. 2, p. 11). JMIR Mental Health.
- Connolly, T., et al. (2012). *A systematic literature review of empirical evidence on computer games and serious games* (Vol. 59, pp. 661–686). Computers & Education.
- Da Matta, A. (2018). *Estratégias diversificadas para o Ensino de Ciências* (p. 82). São Paulo: Pimenta Cultural.
- Dos Santos, J., et al. (2017). *Active methodologies and interdisciplinarity training on the formation of nutritionists* (Vol. 38, pp. 117-128). Semina: Ciências Sociais e Humanas.
- Denami, M. (2018). *Serious game-based learning: the place of users' verbalization in the acquisition of specific skills* (Vol. 22, pp. 144-161). International Journal of Training and Development.
- Fontes, L. & Gontijo, C. (2020). *Active learning methodologies and their contribution to differential and integral calculus teaching*. XII Summer Workshop in Mathematics – UnB.
- Fleming, T., et al. (2017). *Serious games and gamification for mental health: current status and promising directions* (Vol. 7). Frontiers in psychiatry.
- Greipl, S., Moeller, K. & Ninaus, M. (2020) *Potential and limits of game-based learning* (Vol. 12). International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning.
- Gunther, M., Kiesling, E., & Stummer, C. (2011). *Game-based learning in technology management education*. (pp. 191-196), Madrid: IEEE EDUCON 2010 Conference.
- Huang, W., & Soman, D. (2013). *A Practitioner's Guide To Gamification Of Education*. Toronto: Rotman School of Management.
- Milman, N. (2012). *The flipped classroom strategy: What is it and how can it best be used?* (Vol. 11, pp. 9-10). Distance Learning.
- Nakao, O. (2018). *Nova Escola de Engenharia*. Jundiaí: Paco Editorial.
- Oliveira, T., Araújo, I., & Veit, E. (2016). *Aprendizagem Baseada em Equipes (Team-Based Learning): um método ativo para o Ensino de Física*. Caderno Brasileiro de Ensino de Física.
- Pavanelo, E., Germano, J. S. E., & Freitas-Lemes, P. L. (2017). *A interdisciplinaridade em cursos de Engenharia* (pp. 130–148). Revista Docência Do Ensino Superior.
- Ribeiro, C. (2005). *A aprendizagem baseada em problemas (PBL): uma implementação na educação em Engenharia*. São Paulo: Tese de Doutorado, Universidade Federal de São Carlos.
- Silberman, M. (1996). *Active Learning – 101 Strategies do teach any subject*. Massachusetts: Ed. Allyn and Bacon.
- Velho, L., Costa, P., & Goulart, L. (2019). *Gargalos na Formação em Engenharia no Brasil: uma perspectiva dos engenheiros*. (Vol. 15, pp. 1-18) Curitiba: Tecnologia e Sociedade.
- Venturini, S. & Silva, T. (2018). *O uso e benefícios das metodologias ativas em uma disciplina de engenharia de produção* (Vol. 6). Canoas: Revista Unilasalle.

- Whalen, K., et al. (2018). *'All they do is win': Lessons learned from use of a serious game for Circular Economy education* (Vol. 135, pp. 335-345). *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*.
- Zyda, M. (2005). *From visual simulation to virtual reality to games* (Vol. 38, pp. 25-32). *Computer*.